

Privacy Preservation in Textual Data: A Systematic Mapping Study on Differential Privacy and Semantic Similarity

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1. Search String

(“textual data” OR “unstructured text” OR “natural language data” OR corpora OR “sensitive text” OR “private data” OR “confidential document” OR text OR “textual dataset” OR “personal text data” OR “privacy-sensitive textual corpora”) AND (“privacy-preserving techniques” OR “privacy protection” OR “anonymization” OR “pseudonymization” OR “differential privacy” OR “privacy-enhancing” OR “re-identification” OR “semantic similarity” OR “sentence similarity” OR “document similarity” OR “semantic matching” OR “text similarity” OR “cosine similarity” OR “embedding similarity” OR “vector similarity” OR “semantic distance” OR “similarity metrics” OR “lexical similarity” OR “similarity detection”) AND (“interpretability” OR “analytical utility” OR “semantic richness” OR “text clustering” OR “topic modeling” OR “document classification” OR “privacy protection” OR “risk mitigation” OR “data anonymization” OR “balance between utility and privacy” OR “privacy-utility trade-off” OR “knowledge extraction” OR “meaning preservation”) AND (“Natural language processing” OR NLP OR “Information retrieval” OR “Privacy in AI” OR “Responsible AI” OR “Ethical AI” OR “Legal NLP” OR “AI agents” OR “Autonomous agents” OR “Conversational AI” OR “Large language models” OR “LLM” OR “Foundation models” OR “Data science”)